

The zeta(s) function. Endless spirals in search of their origin.

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This revision equals to a deletion.
Instead I want to point out two of my preprints on the same topic.

Riemann's Hypothesis. This is why it is true.
Traces of the Riemann zeta function on the complex plane.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6654333>

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026759>

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04/09/2023